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MAIN OUTCOMES OF HEIBUS PROJECT AND FUTURE COOPERATION OF ITS PARTNERS

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ABSTRACT

Smart HEI-Business collaboration for skills and competitiveness (HEIBus) was Erasmus + Knowledge Alliances 2 (KA2) project with a budget of about one million euros and a duration of 36 months (1 January 2017 – 31 December 2019). The project focused on strengthening the collaboration between HEIs (High Education Institutions) and companies by developing and testing new, smart and innovative cooperation models for HEI-company cooperation and methods for teaching. The project brought together HEIs and companies from five European countries with strong expertise and experience in different fields. These models and methods facilitated the involvement of students, HEI educators and company experts in international and multidisciplinary Research & Development & Innovation (R&D&I) projects proposed by companies.

During HEIBus project all HEI and company partners worked hard and took part intensively in all their own project activities. All goals of the project were achieved very well and some of them were even exceeded, for example one extra Multidisciplinary Real Life Problem Solving project was carried out. After the project all partners are really satisfy for the outcomes and want to continue, deepen and widen cooperation.

During the Coronavirus pandemic it has been very clearly noticed how important it is to use effectively virtual methods which were a lot tested and practised in this project.

1 BASIC INFORMATION OF THE HEIBUS PROJECT

1.1 Aims of the HEIBus project

It is important that the needs of working life are matched with the education provided. This is an ongoing process and can only be reached with continuing and fluent HEI-company cooperation.

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The aim of the Smart HEI-Business collaboration for skills and competitiveness (HEIBus, www.heibus.eu) project was to increase, improve, widen and deepen HEI-company cooperation at the student and the expert levels, promoting innovation, flexibility and entrepreneurial thinking.

The project focused on strengthening and deepening the collaboration between HEIs and companies by creating new innovative cooperation models. These models facilitated the involvement of students and educators of HEIs and experts of companies in international Research & Development & Innovation (R&D&I) projects proposed by companies.

1.2 Partners

The HEIBus project consisted of five university partners and seven company partners from five different European countries (Finland, Germany, Hungary, Romania and Spain) as full partners:

- JAMK University of Applied Sciences (JAMK, main partner, www.jamk.fi/en/) and ITAB Finland Oy (www.itab.fi/en/) from Finland
- Technical University of Cluj-Napoca (TUCLUJ, www.utcluj.ro/en/), SC PRO Tehnic (www.pro-tehnic.ro) and Automates ACM SRL (www.automatesacm.ro) from Romania
- University of Miskolc (ME, www.uni-miskolc.hu/en/), Electrolux (www.electrolux.com) and Robert Bosch Power Tool (www.bosch-garden.com/gb/en) from Hungary
- University of Applied Sciences Esslingen (HE, www.hs-esslingen.de/en/) and Stoebich (www.stoebich.com) from Germany
- University of Jaen (UJA, www.ujaen.es/serv/vicint/home/index) and Valeo Lighting Systems (www.valeo.com/en) from Spain.

The group of partners consisted of SMEs as well as some large companies. Three HEI partners were academic universities while two were universities of applied sciences. The partnership comprised a perfect variety of different types of organisations and professionals. This provided very interesting and fruitful cooperation with different perspectives on each aspect of the project. Also 17 associated partner companies and institutions and several external partners around Europe followed the progress, utilised the results or took part in some of the project activities.

1.3 Work packages

In HEIBus project there were 8 work packages which are Management (WP1), Best practices of HEI-company cooperation (WP2), Multidisciplinary Real Life Problem Solving (WP3), Expert Level Real Life Problem Solving (WP4), Flexible Student Mentoring by Companies (WP5), Quality Assurance (WP6), Evaluation (WP7) and Dissemination & Exploitation (WP8). Four of them (WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5) were implementation work packages which will be explained deeper in the following chapters.

2 METHODOLOGY

Cooperation between HEIs and companies is not a new concept. There are cooperation programmes, which date back to the first decade of the 20th century [1] or are well-known internationally that have served as a reference model [2]. In HEIBus project the methodology shown in Fig. 1 was implemented with the aim to identify and analyze the existing cooperation models around the world providing real life experiences between HEIs and companies.

Fig. 1. Methodologies to identify the best existing models of HEI-company cooperation. (a) Interaction between HEI student and HEI expert with company; (b) Company involvement in HEI education

As can be seen, the analyses of HEI and company cooperation models follow the same procedure (Fig. 1a) with the exception of the analysis of company involvement in HEI education (Fig. 1b).

In the Best Practices of HEI-Company Cooperation work package (WP2) it was carried out the identification and analyzing of the existing cooperation models providing real-life experiences between HEIs and companies in the following way:

- to analyse the state-of-the-art HEI student-company cooperation models
- to analyse the state-of-the-art HEI expert-company cooperation models
- to analyse different platforms and forums used in HEI-company communication
- to analyse the best practices on company involvement in HEI education.

Descriptions of existing cooperation models and the main WP2 tasks are in Table 1.

Table 1. Existing cooperation models and the main tasks of work package 2

Student-company cooperation models	HEI expert-company cooperation models	Internet based platforms for HEI-company communication	Company involvement in HEI education models	Coaching for virtual activities
To search different existing methods or models	To search existing models	To find and analyse 15 internet based platforms	To search different existing methods or models	To ensure effective participation of all partners in virtual activities
To find at least 10 good and beneficial models	To find at least 10 good and beneficial models	To search best practices for communication	To search different levels of involvement	To organizes coaching of virtual methods

To select 5 models for deeper analysis	To select 5 models for deeper analysis	To build a new platform or to join in best available platform	To analyse different levels of involvement	To use social media for different project activities
To form background for the Multidisciplinary student level real life problem solving (WP3)	To form background for the Expert level real life problem solving (WP4)	To help continuation of the HEIBus activities after the project	To form background for the Flexible student mentoring by companies (WP5)	To invite associated partners to take part in virtual coaching

Work package leaders searched existing methods and models for HEI-company cooperation and they selected the best models for deeper analyses [3]. Regarding the outcomes of this work package, the common opinion of HEIBus partners was that the best and most comprehensive ideas and models for HEI-company cooperation were found. These models formed a good background for the other implementation work packages, WP3-WP5, which are introduced in the next chapter.

3 IMPLEMENTATION, RESULTS AND FEEDBACKS OF HEIBUS MODELS

The HEIBus project developed its own specific models for each of the former ways of cooperation. Following sub-sections present a brief overview of these models and also the main results and feedbacks of the implementations. Detailed descriptions can be found in [4] and [5].

3.1 Multidisciplinary Real Life Problem Solving (RLPS, WP3)

The idea of RLPS model was that students from different study programs and nationalities formed three mixed, international and multidisciplinary groups in order to solve a real-life problem proposed by the project company and to compete each other. Fig. 3 shows a diagram of the RLPS model.

Fig. 3. RLPS model

The project started with an intensive week, hosted by the HEI whose company partner offered the topic. During this week, two international student groups had face-to-face meetings while the third group had them in a virtual way. After the intensive week, all three groups worked virtually and were supervised by the

company tutors and the HEI supervisors. At the end of the project, the company tutors selected a winning solution and group and HEI supervisors evaluated students.

During the intensive week it is very important to focus on the tailored lectures and to explain what the students really need to know from the specific task. There is no added value for example to explain random company information which only takes away the precious time needed for team work. Good English language skill level is needed for all participants: students, HEI supervisors and company tutors.

Advanced computer program(s) and good meeting equipments, for example a meeting microphone and a webcam, and also a suitable and silent meeting place are needed to have in every participating HEI. It is also very important to have guidance In the beginning of every RLPS project, HEI supervisors had a meeting with students where they explained how to use right and effectively needed equipments.

After six original RLPS projects, collected feedbacks showed that many students and supervisors would have appreciated another intensive week. The 7th RLPS project included another intensive week in the middle of the project period. The opinion of students and supervisors was that this modified version of RLPS was very good and workable. All feedback surveys showed that the implementation way of RLPS projects was very innovative way to study and extremely useful for their future. All HEI supervisors and company tutors mentioned that RLPS projects should definitely be continued on the created and tested ways in the future, too.

It has been interesting and rewarding to read the success stories of students who have found internship, final thesis and/or permanent work place at the project company after taking part in RLPS project.

3.2 Expert Level Real Life Problem Solving (EXPERT, WP4)

In the EXPERT project, the project company gave a more complex problem than in the RLPS project which a group of international and multidisciplinary experts of three HEIs solved together with the company experts, see *Fig. 4*.

Fig. 4. EXPERT model

The EXPERT project started with face-to-face kick-off days hosted by the HEI, whose company partner offered the topic. The kick-off days contained a visit at the project company and team working sessions at the host HEI. Then, about four month time, the experts worked at their own HEIs and the company, meet each other only in virtual meetings and finalised the project.

The feedback surveys showed that EXPERT model promoted innovation and knowledge transfer between HEIs and companies as well as increased the skills of the HEI experts and the working life relevance of education.

EXPERT projects offered the opportunity for HEI experts from three countries to collaborate closely with company experts in a joint research project with direct impact in everyday life of the company. EXPERT projects helped HEI experts in increasing their know-how of the work field with great potential of implementing the new info in the teaching materials. In the same time close connection with the company helped to create an international network of experts and to find new topics for future projects. EXPERT model seems to be very good and suitable for the demanding international projects.

The EXPERT work package also included the building of a virtual Expert Support Service (ESS, www.heibus.eu/experts), which allows easy and quick access for all companies looking for expert services by HEIs. The ESS offers direct expert contacts for starting an EXPERT project and possibility to ask quick support for smaller problems.

3.3 Flexible Student Mentoring by Companies (Flex Mentoring, WP5)

The HEIBus project tested flexible ways to involve companies in the education process of students. Each HEI and company chose the involvement level and method best suited to them. Flexibility came from the different levels of involvement. The most common and used methods were: tailored lectures, supervision of projects and laboratory work and dedicated courses given by company mentors, visits and trainings at companies and also workshops, seminars and fairs, where students cooperated with company representatives.

The company mentors acted as godparents for a certain student group and in the same time they had possibility to do long-lasting recruiting and to find the most suitable students and future engineers for their needs.

The commitment of company mentors and students is important for the whole project period. Fluent communication between company mentors and students is essential and it helps to maintain the high motivation for everyone. It is also important to find a suitable company for a certain student group.

The main outcomes of Flexible Mentoring projects were increased motivation and study success for students, easy recruitment and a good labour force for companies and good knowledge transfer between HEIs and companies.

4 OUTCOMES AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

4.1 Main outcomes of HEIBus

During the kick-off meeting of the HEIBus project the main contact persons of all partners got info and supervision for effective virtual meeting arrangements and they practiced together how to use needed equipments. These main contact persons were the key persons for supervising other staff members and students at their own organisations to use the equipments of virtual meetings. This guarantees that after the HEIBus project it is easy for all partners to carry out virtual meetings.

Experiences of the totally and partly virtual RLPS and partly virtual EXPERT projects have been very important to share and spread worldwide especially during the time of crisis such as Coronavirus pandemic. Online meetings, teaching, supervising and mentoring have become the new normal, so collected and shared experiences of the HEIBus project are valuable for everyone.

The feedback surveys of RLPS projects showed that the common opinion of students, HEI supervisors and company tutors was that these projects were successful, rewarding and very innovative way to study and cooperate. All students informed that they also came more international and improved their English language skill.

The feedback surveys of EXPERT projects showed that all HEI and company experts found these projects excellent, effective and innovative way to cooperate and solve complicated problems. In the same time HEI experts increased their knowledge of the project company and company experts their knowledge of three international HEIs. All experts informed that they want definitely take part in new EXPERT projects in the future.

The HEIBus models have their own distinguished features. Because the HEIBus was an international project, features such as multilingual, multidisciplinary and virtual work were included in all its implementations and made them unique.

Three HEIBus models and outcomes of their implementations have been introduced in several national and international conference publications and presentations, professional articles, TV and radio interviews which can be found at HEIBus web site. HEIBus partners are continuing cooperation and implementations of all three cooperation models. Here some examples:

- Finnish and German HEI partners together decided to implement a tailored RLPS project in every academic year by financial help of own HEIs and other HEI partners are planning to continue RLPS projects one way or another
- HEI partners are together searching new possible ways to carry out RLPS and EXPERT projects without EU grant
- All companies can use the virtual Expert Support Service (ESS) to find the best and most suitable HEI experts for their needs
- HEI partners are continuing to carry out Flexible Mentoring projects with the company partners they cooperated during HEIBus project
- HEI partners introduce and invite new company partners for Flexible Mentoring projects

This means that in the future there will come new outcomes and be created new publications which can be found at HEIBus web site. In the future the dissemination of HEIBus outcomes will continue and widen in the educational field.

4.2 Knowledge transfer after the HEIBus project

At the HEIBus web site (www.heibus.eu) under Intellectual Outputs – Public Project Reports there is “RLPS Implementation Guide” where can be found for example Step-by-Step-Guide, Checklist and Model of Intensive Week reports. There are also “Process model for international expert cooperation”, “Information sheet about international expert cooperation” and “Info materials for Flex Mentoring program” reports. These reports consist a lot important and valuable information and make it easy for new HEIs and companies to copy these three models and carry out new RLPS, EXPERT and Flex Mentoring projects themselves.

During the HEIBus project HEI partners also cooperated with new international cooperation partners and took part in the application work of new international projects which at least partly base on the HEIBus cooperation models. Some of the proposals have already accepted and projects have started, for example the EIT Raw Materials project (<https://eitrawmaterials.eu>) and Erasmus ICM project between University of Miskolc (ME, Hungary) and University Guru Nanak Dev (India). Three HEI partners (JAMK, TUCLUJ and UJA) took part in the application work of a new Knowledge Alliances 2 (KA2) project and got the positive feedback from EU in the end of July 2020. The name of this project is Processing Complexity with Emotional, Sensorial and Spiritual Capacities (ProCESS) and its main HEI partner is Catholic University of Lyon (France). The ProCESS project will start in the end of year 2020. All three HEIBus project models will be introduced and published later this year as good and innovative cooperation examples in the Circular Economy Competence of Universities of Applied Sciences project funded by the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture (<https://kiertotalousamk.turkuamk.fi/kiertotalousamk/>).

HEIBus partners will further create professional and scientific papers of HEIBus models and project outcomes for national and international conferences. All accepted papers and new outcomes can be found at HEIBus web site in the future.

5 SUMMARY

Based on the best practices of HEI-company cooperation, it can be concluded that the HEIBus project created innovative models for HEI student-company and HEI expert-company cooperation. Features such as: multilingual, multidisciplinary, international, innovative, virtual team work, applicability of student evaluated by the company are included, all together, in the HEIBus models. Implementations of HEIBus project were effective ways of strengthening and widening the collaboration among all HEI and company partners. Feedbacks of all partners were very positive and they learned a lot from each other and from new kinds of cooperation. All partners want to continue, widen and deepen cooperation, which was one goal of the project.

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